

EFFECTIVENESS OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF ORIENTAL AND SWEET VARIETIES OF DOMESTIC WATERMELON

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Annotation: Currently, the goal clearly pursued by our state from the application of water-intensive irrigation technologies in agricultural products is to obtain high yields. At the same time, the scientific justification of optimal irrigation regimes, along with the use of domestic watermelon along with modern irrigation technologies, is also considered to be an increase in productivity.

Keywords: watermelon, watering, regime, time, variety, field, drip, soil, resource, hydromodule.

In 2022, the planting of watermelon and melon crops on an area of 158,894 hectares was established by farms and agricultural enterprises in Uzbekistan. To date, 114,790 hectares of pulses have been planted on the main area, garden-vine rows and Tulip lands. A total of 510.9 thousand tons were produced from these fields. Also, 30.1 thousand hectares of land vacated by the galla were planted with paddy crops. Since the beginning of the year, 74.7 thousand tons of melons and 431.6 thousand tons of watermelons have been grown. To obtain a rich and high-quality harvest of watermelon, seeds are sown with a variety of 99 percent and a germination of no less than 90-95 percent. To speed up the germination of seeds and achieve a 100 percent result, the copper cuporo before planting is ivitized for 1 hour in a 0.5-1.0 percent solution. Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) is a species of flowering plant in the legume family, Fabaceae. There is a stem similar to a vine (vine) plant. It is a hammabop range product with more than 1000 varieties worldwide. Watermelon is grown worldwide - in favorable climates from the tropics to temperate regions - for its large edible fruit: it is a berry without hard bark and internal divisions. Sweet,

juicy, the flesh is usually dark red to pink, with many black seeds, sometimes there are also seedless varieties. The fruit can be eaten raw or pickled. It can also be consumed by mixing it into juice or drinks. The Kordofan in Sudan is conspecific with melons, which may be descendants of the watermelons cultivated today. Wild watermelon seeds were found in the Uan Mukhuggiag in Libya, which dates back to about 3500 BC. Watermelons were cultured in Northeast Africa and cultivated in Egypt around 2000 BC. They were different from the present sweet watermelons. The watermelons we eat today were spread throughout the Mediterranean world in Roman times. Work within the framework of large yields has created a variety of disease-resistant varieties. There are many varieties that bear fruit matured within 100 days of planting in the breeding Hoha. In 2017, China produced two-thirds of the world's total watermelon

Watermelon care: The care of this field crop consists of plant yaganization, soil loosening, crop feeding, chopping, irrigation, plowing, weed control, and pest control. Fairy watermelon products are grown using methods such as soil mulching, planting crops from seedlings, mulching from seedlings and seeds under a temporary film-cover, growing in protected heated and unheated greenhouses. Despite the fact that watermelon is very resistant to drought, in Republican conditions it must be watered and cared for. However, excessive sernam soil negatively affects the watermelon crop. In Sernam soil, the sugar content in the fruit decreases, the peel thickens, develops various fungal diseases, including fusariosis-wilting disease.

Types: In Uzbekistan, 47 varieties of watermelon are zoned. Of these, 15 are domestic and the rest are foreign varieties. Varieties such as "Dilnoz", "Manzur", "Lamb-30", "Hayit Black", "sweet Oriental delicacy" are considered local.

Harvest: The first harvest is obtained in the third decade of June, the second in the first half of June and the third in the third decade of may. In the repeated period, the sown watermelon matures in the third decade of September and is picked into a rootstock. Of course, the ripening period of the watermelon can vary depending on the weather, soil conditions, planting times, early or mid-ripening of the varieties. Plants reach 4 m in length. They have a curved line. Regardless of the fact that the fruits of the culture are very large, the stalk will be very delicate. Culture sheets have an ovoid shape and flaws along the edges. Length 10-20 cm, width 6-17 CM. Plant flowers in summer. The flowers are mostly white. The Balcent grows in the form of a boat. The fruits of the culture have a lot of seeds. The pulp is juicy and Soft, has a red or pink color in the

form of rock. The fruit is sweet.

The procedure for sowing watermelon seeds is as follows: On the site, it is recommended to plant planting material when the soil warms up to 13 degrees of sunlight. To do this, the seeds are kept with warm water until the branches are processed. On the site chosen for planting a culture, sheep's wings are produced to a depth of 10 cm. Patterns are located at a distance of 100 cm. Fertilizers are placed in the landing hole (Humidia with the addition of 1 art. L. Ash and 1 tbs. Ammopos). In addition, the seeds are placed in a well and sprinkled on top of the soil. The first branches should appear after 10-14 days. The belief must be correct (weak shoots).

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